

Prevalence Of Dry Socket In Surgically Removed Impacted Teeth

Research Article

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Abstract

To assess the prevalence of dry socket in surgically removed impacted teeth. A retrospective study was done in an institutional setting. The data for the study was retrieved from the college patient records. All the patients who underwent surgical removal of impacted teeth were given a time frame of June 2019 - March 2020, were taken into consideration. The patient details included name, age, gender, tooth number and patient intra oral state and complaint on recall visits were retrieved from the software. The data was then analysed using SPSS software. Total of 362 patients were involved in this study, 218 being male patients and 144 being female patients. A total of 17 cases (4.7%) reported back with dry socket out of the 362 cases included in the study. More cases of dry socket was seen in the mandibular third molars. The age group in which dry socket was more prevalent was between 21-30 years age group. Dry socket was most commonly seen in mandibular third molars, a total of 17 cases reported back with dry socket out of the 362 cases included.

Keywords: Alveolar Osteitis; Third Molar Surgery; Wisdom Teeth; Post Operative Complication; Impacted Teeth.

Introduction

Third molars are the last to erupt and have high chances of becoming impacted, teeth may become impacted when they fail to erupt or develop into proper functional location. Impacted teeth are considered non functional and abnormal. One of the main reasons for the teeth to get impacted is space deficiency. One of the most important and common complications following surgical removal of impacted teeth is dry socket. This phenomenon is due to resolution of blood clot and exposure of alveolar bone. Pain, halitosis, activity reduction, and additional returns to visit surgeon are of costs patient will pay. [16, 15]. Many factors lead to development of dry sockets, some of them are general health of patients, professional factors and local factors. Elder patients are at a higher risk of developing dry socket. One of the most important factors to be considered that plays a major role in development of dry socket is surgeon's lack of experience and patience and poor oral hygiene maintenance. The aim of this study is to evaluate the prevalence of dry socket in surgically re-

moved impacted teeth. This study will give us an idea on how often dry sockets occur and the points to keep in mind while doing impaction to avoid the occurrence of dry socket.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective study was conducted in an institutional setting. The ethical clearance was obtained from the institute's ethical committee. The study involved all the patients who had undergone surgical removal of impacted teeth in a given time frame.

Selection Of Subjects

All patients who had undergone surgical removal of impacted teeth were considered in this study. The time period of choice was from June 2019 to March 2020. A total of 86000 patients were reviewed and analysed. There were three people involved in this study - the guide, reviewer and researcher. All available data was

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collected and sorted.

Data Collection

The patient details were retrieved from the institution's patient records. Data regarding the patient's age, gender, tooth number and intra oral state and complaint of patient were considered for this study. Cross verification of the data was done by the second reviewer, to avoid any missing or repetitive data. The data was manually retrieved and tabulated in excel and sorted.

Inclusion Criteria

All patients who underwent surgical removal of impacted teeth were included in this study. All age groups were considered.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with incomplete case records were not included in the study. Repetitive entries were also excluded.

Statistical Analysis

The tabulated data was analysed using SPSS software (IBM SPSS statistics 260). The method of analysis that was used was “chi square test”. The analysis was done between age and occurrence of dry socket and also between tooth and occurrence of dry socket.

Results and Discussion

The above study was to determine the prevalence of dry socket in surgically removed impacted teeth.

Data Analysis: Out of the 362 patients who under went surgical removal of impacted teeth, 17 cases (4.7%) cases reported back with dry socket (figure 1). When age was compared with the diagnosis post impaction procedure it was found out that most number of dry sockets occurred in the age group ranging from 21-30 years and when tooth number was compared with diagnosis it was found that the most common teeth to be affected by dry socket was the mandibular molars(Fig 2). On comparison between gender and diagnosis it was found that out of 144 female patients 8 cases were diagnosed as dry socket. While on the other hand out of 218 male patients 9 patients were diagnosed with dry socket. The above mentioned data have been depicted as pie charts and

Figure 1. 17 cases of 362 cases reported back with dry socket.

Figure 2. X axis - tooth number, Y axis - number of dry socket cases.

This study showed an increased number of cases of dry socket in the lower mandibular wisdom teeth. P value is 0.362, statistically insignificant.

Figure 3. X axis - age group of patients (range denotes 0-10 as 1, 11-20 as 2 21-30 as 3 31-40 as 4 and so on...), Y axis - diagnosis.

The study showed an increased number of dry socket cases in the age group 21-30 years.

Group. P value is 0.83 , statistically insignificant

Figure 4. X axis- gender, Y axis- diagnosis
The study showed very less difference in occurrence of dry socket in both the genders (more in males than females). P value is 0.530, statistically insignificant.

graphs below.

Surgical removal of impacted 3rd molar is a common procedure which is routinely carried out in dental offices. The removed teeth showed all kinds of impaction, so the procedures varied from simple impactions to difficult cases. Complication can arise following third molar surgery that could range from infection, ulcer, swelling, paraesthesia and trismus. These complications are well documented. Dry socket starts 1 to 3 days after extraction with severe pain, halitosis, foul taste, and regional lymphadenitis [20, 15] [8]. Clinical examination, there exists no blood clot in the socket and the bone is exposed [6, 12] [5].

The results of the current study revealed that prevalence of dry socket following surgical extraction of impacted mandibular third molar were 4.75%. This finding is not in accordance with the incidence rate between 5% and 30% reported in various previous studies [2, 3, 17]. This could possibly be attributed to the different assessment methods and the variations in diagnostic criteria.

Infection increases the release of tissue activators from the alveolar bone which leads to enhanced fibrinolytic activity and loss of blood clot [7, 9, 19]. In addition, trauma could also increase the release of tissue activators and the incidence of dry socket [7, 18, 22] The surgeon experience effect on the amount of trauma in an extraction. Observed higher incidence of postoperative complication (including DS) in surgeries by residents when compared with oral and maxillofacial surgeons [11, 1, 15].

Regarding anatomical site, mandibular teeth, were more affected than maxillary teeth, consistent with a study conducted in Sri Lanka. More commonly cases were noted in the mandibular 3rd molars. The specificity of these sites may be related to the decreased vascularity, greater bone density and a diminished capacity in forming granulation tissue. It has also been suggested that difficulty of traumatic extractions may be a cause. It is thought that trauma results in compression of the alveolar bone, reduction in blood [13, 1] perfusion and thrombosis of underlying blood vessels leading to increased fibrinolytic activity.

Dry socket incidence is age dependent. Although, the peak age varies among different reports, most of the research works reveal 20 to 40 years of age as the peak period of dry socket incidence [10, 14, 21] In the above mentioned study the age group in which dry socket was most prevalent was between 21-30 years.

Conflicting results exist according to the role of gender. Sweet and Butler found incidence of DS in women eight times more

than men [25][26, 27] However, Catellani, Al-khateeb et al and Nusair and Younes concluded that gender has no effect on Dry socket which is in accordance with the result of the above done study [4] [23]. It should be mentioned that in western countries a higher number of women smoke. But in eastern countries including our current study, the number of smoker women is scare [24].

Conclusion

The occurrence of dry socket in an everyday oral surgery or dental practice is unavoidable. Dry socket occurrence is a painful but infrequent complication of tooth extraction and most commonly affects the mandibular teeth. Oral contraception and smoking independently or in combination with a traumatic extraction were the most prevalent predisposing factors for dry socket. Surgeons must recognize additional risk factors in patients with particular medical conditions and include this information as a part of the informed consent. Treatment options for this condition are generally limited and directed toward palliative care. The surgical site should be irrigated, avoiding curetting the extraction socket. Packing with a zinc oxide-eugenol paste on iodoform gauze can be considered to relieve acute pain episodes. Ultimately it is the host's healing potential which determines the severity and duration of the condition.

References

- [1]. Abhinav RP, Selvarasu K, Maheswari GU, Taltia AA. The Patterns and Etiology of Maxillofacial Trauma in South India. *Ann Maxillofac Surg*. 2019 Jan-Jun; 9(1): 114-117. PMID: 31293938.
- [2]. al-Khateeb TL, el-Marsafi AI, Butler NP. The relationship between the indications for the surgical removal of impacted third molars and the incidence of alveolar osteitis. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 1991 Feb; 49(2): 141-5. PMID: 1990091.
- [3]. Blum IR. Contemporary views on dry socket (alveolar osteitis): a clinical appraisal of standardization, aetiopathogenesis and management: a critical review. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 2002 Jun; 31(3): 309-17. PMID: 12190139.
- [4]. Catellani JE. Review of factors contributing to dry socket through enhanced fibrinolysis. *J Oral Surg*. 1979 Jan; 37(1): 42-6. PMID: 363986.
- [5]. Christabel A, Anantanarayanan P, Subash P, Soh CL, Ramanathan M, Muthusekhar MR, et al. Comparison of pterygomaxillary dysjunction with tuberosity separation in isolated Le Fort I osteotomies: a prospective, multi-centre, triple-blind, randomized controlled trial. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 2016 Feb; 45(2): 180-5. PMID: 26338075.
- [6]. Hermes CB, Hilton TJ, Biesbrock AR, Baker RA, Cain-Hamlin J, McClanahan SF, et al. Perioperative use of 0.12% chlorhexidine gluconate for the prevention of alveolar osteitis: efficacy and risk factor analysis. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*. 1998 Apr; 85(4): 381-7. PMID: 9574945.
- [7]. Hita-Iglesias P, Torres-Lagares D, Flores-Ruiz R, Magallanes-Abad N, Ballellote-Gonzalez M, Gutierrez-Perez JL. Effectiveness of chlorhexidine gel

- versus chlorhexidine rinse in reducing alveolar osteitis in mandibular third molar surgery. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2008 Mar; 66(3): 441-5. PMID: 18280375.
- [8]. Jesudasan JS, Wahab PU, Sekhar MR. Effectiveness of 0.2% chlorhexidine gel and a eugenol-based paste on postoperative alveolar osteitis in patients having third molars extracted: a randomised controlled clinical trial. *Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2015 Nov; 53(9): 826-30. PMID: 26188932.
- [9]. Song PC, Schwartz J, Blitzer A. The emerging role of botulinum toxin in the treatment of temporomandibular disorders. *Oral Dis.* 2007 May; 13(3): 253-60. PMID: 17448205.
- [10]. MacGregor AJ. Aetiology of dry socket: a clinical investigation. *Br J Oral Surg.* 1968 Jul; 6(1): 49-58. PMID: 5244107.
- [11]. MacGregor AJ. The impacted lower wisdom tooth. Oxford University Press, USA; 1985.
- [12]. Marimuthu M, Andiappan M, Wahab A, Muthusekhar MR, Balakrishnan A, Shanmugam S. Canonical Wnt pathway gene expression and their clinical correlation in oral squamous cell carcinoma. *Indian J Dent Res.* 2018 May-Jun; 29(3): 291-297. PMID: 29900911.
- [13]. Mary DJ. Incidence, number and laterality of epipteric bones in the pterion in dry human skulls of south india. *International Journal of Current Advanced Research.* 2017; 3198-3200.
- [14]. Kumar S, Rahman RE. Knowledge, awareness, and practices regarding biomedical waste management among undergraduate dental students. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2017; 10(8): 341.
- [15]. Mp SK, Sneha S. Knowledge And Awareness Regarding Antibiotic Prophylaxis For Infective Endocarditis Among Undergraduate Dental Students. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2016; 154-159.
- [16]. Osborn TP, Frederickson G Jr, Small IA, Torgerson TS. A prospective study of complications related to mandibular third molar surgery. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 1985 Oct; 43(10): 767-9. PMID: 2995624.
- [17]. Packiri S, Gurunathan D, Selvarasu K. Management of Paediatric Oral Ranula: A Systematic Review. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2017 Sep; 11(9): ZE06-ZE09. PMID: 29207849.
- [18]. Patil SB, Durairaj D, Suresh Kumar G, Karthikeyan D, Pradeep D. Comparison of Extended Nasolabial Flap Versus Buccal Fat Pad Graft in the Surgical Management of Oral Submucous Fibrosis: A Prospective Pilot Study. *J Maxillofac Oral Surg.* 2017 Sep; 16(3): 312-321. PMID: 28717289.
- [19]. Patturaja K, Pradeep D. Awareness of Basic Dental Procedure among General Population. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology.* 2016 Sep 1; 9(9): 1349.
- [20]. Peterson LJ. Peterson's principles of oral and maxillofacial surgery. PMPH-USA; 2012.
- [21]. Rahman RE, Mp SK. Knowledge, attitude, and awareness of dental undergraduate students regarding human immunodeficiency virus/acquired immunodeficiency syndrome patients. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res [Internet].* 2017; 10(5): 175-80.
- [22]. Rao TD, Kumar MS. Analgesic efficacy of paracetamol vs ketorolac after dental extractions. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology.* 2018 Aug 1; 11(8): 3375-9.
- [23]. Ravikumar KK, Narayanan V. Prediction of postoperative outcome in mandibular third molar surgery based on preoperative variables: A Prospective clinical study. *International Journal of Social Rehabilitation.* 2018 Jan 1; 3(1):14.
- [24]. Sanikop S, Agrawal P, Patil S. Relationship between dental anxiety and pain perception during scaling. *J Oral Sci.* 2011 Sep; 53(3): 341-8. PMID: 21959662.
- [25]. Sweet JB, Butler DP. Predisposing and operative factors: effect on the incidence of localized osteitis in mandibular third-molar surgery. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1978 Aug; 46(2): 206-15. PMID: 280828.
- [26]. Sweta VR, Abhinav RP, Ramesh A. Role of Virtual Reality in Pain Perception of Patients Following the Administration of Local Anesthesia. *Ann Maxillofac Surg.* 2019 Jan-Jun; 9(1): 110-113. PMID: 31293937.
- [27]. Vijayakumar Jain S, Muthusekhar MR, Baig MF, Senthilnathan P, Loganathan S, Abdul Wahab PU, et al. Evaluation of Three-Dimensional Changes in Pharyngeal Airway Following Isolated Lefort One Osteotomy for the Correction of Vertical Maxillary Excess: A Prospective Study. *J Maxillofac Oral Surg.* 2019 Mar; 18(1): 139-146. PMID: 30728705.